

Intergenerational social mobility and the ambivalent role of higher education: a systematic review

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ABSTRACT

University education has historically been considered a means of upward social mobility. However, recent studies question this equalizing role, finding substantial differences in the “rewards” it represents according to social class. Thus, the objective of this research is to analyze the relationship between having university studies and experiencing intergenerational social mobility in today’s world. For this purpose, a systematic review of the literature was carried out under a qualitative approach. A bibliographic search was carried out in academic data bases of renowned prestige, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and ERIC. Specific search terms such as “intergenerational social mobility”, “university education” and “inequality” were also used, considering the period between 2014 and 2024. A total of 28 articles were analyzed. The findings show that, while graduates with professional parents effectively capitalize on the educational credential, those who come first in their families face more barriers to translating the degree into occupational mobility. Socioeconomic origin also delimits trajectories within universities and impacts on dropout, graduation, and differentiated academic performance. Consequently, the magnitude of this mobility varies significantly by social origin, with graduates from professional or academic families demonstrating a markedly greater ability to leverage their educational credentials in the labor market.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Intergenerational social mobility refers to a change in the socioeconomic status of individuals relative to their parents. This concept has been pivotal in sociological investigations since the mid-20th century [1]–[3]. This phenomenon has garnered significant attention due to its profound implications for social equality, economic development, and the overall structure of society [4]–[6]. The study of this construct provides insights into the fluidity of social structures and the efficiency of mechanisms designed to promote equality of opportunity, particularly in access to higher education [7]–[9]. This perspective is grounded in the belief that university education acts as an equalizer by providing the knowledge, skills, and credentials necessary to transcend socio-economic roots [10], [11]. However, it should not be seen merely as

a pathway to social progress but also as a key driver of social mobility and human capital development at the family level. The transformative power of higher education extends far beyond the acquisition of academic knowledge. It facilitates access to diverse social groups, which can be instrumental in professional development [12]–[16]. Furthermore, it equips citizens with valuable knowledge and skills for the labor market, thereby offering critical opportunities to enter professional spheres [17], [18]. Additionally, the university experience fosters the development of socioemotional and adaptive skills essential for long-term professional success [19]–[21]. Nevertheless, in the first decades of the 21st century, a challenge has arisen that defies conventional wisdom regarding higher education's role in reducing social inequality. In this context, empirical studies have examined the extent to which this function is being fulfilled in the contemporary global landscape.

Despite the global expansion of higher education systems, there remain significant breaches for its access, especially for low-income people, ethnical minorizes and possible first-generation students. These discrepancies reflect structural disconformity of social, economic and educational order. Therefore, this inequality in access to universities highlights the necessity to explore the interaction between higher education and social structures, which challenges the simplest notions of education as an automatic equalizer.

Therefore, it is important to highlight that this literature review can expose the degree to which higher education contributes to upward social mobility by strengthening human capital and developing specific skills for the creation and application of knowledge. It also analyzes the factors that link it to the improvement of economic conditions, health, well-being and employability of those who aspire to a university degree. On the other hand, it also makes it possible to identify the obstacles that perpetuate social inequality by limiting the opportunities of new generations and hindering the access of the first generations due to the lack of family support.

As a consequence, the present study has the objective of identifying patterns and tendencies in the current literature, emphasizing the relation between university studies and intergenerational social mobility in the contemporary world. In this regard, this investigation has the intention of giving an answer to the following questions: what is the current role of higher education in the intergenerational social mobility? How is the nature of the recent patterns of intergenerational social mobility? Also, what is the perspective intergenerational social mobility? The answer to these questions will be key to understand how the life conditions of a generation can impact the progress of the next generations. Likewise, we will try to address situations like equity, monitoring of the economic impact and identifying potential social barriers.

2. METHOD

The present research adopts a qualitative-interpretative approach with an exploratory design, implementing a systematic review of the available literature on intergenerational social mobility and the role of university education. This process rigorously adheres to the guidelines of the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses method (PRISMA), which highlights the stages of a systematized and relevant search, the relevant selection under inclusion and exclusion criteria, the description of the design and type of article, and the interpretative synthesis of the results, thus inducing the reduction of bias in the study [22]. This methodology facilitates an in-depth analysis of the influence of higher education on patterns of social mobility in the region, highlighting both its positive aspects and its ambivalent implications. The study is based on exhaustive documentary analysis of secondary sources, with emphasis on research published in indexed academic journals, reports issued by international organizations, and official documents related to educational and social policies in the region. The methodology employed is based on the systematic compilation, rigorous categorization, and critical analysis of these documents, to identify and examine the patterns of social mobility associated with university education in the global context.

The bibliographic search was carried out in academic databases of recognized prestige, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Eric, considering the period 2014–2024. These were selected according to the thematic area of the research, which involves the social sciences and educational sciences; in addition, the studies indexed in the databases guarantee a significant level of quality, as well as a great temporal and spatial amplitude, in terms of the data and impact of the publications. They also reduce the probability of bias in the selection of articles [23]. Specific search terms were also used, such as “intergenerational social mobility”, “university education” and “inequality”, as seen in Table 1. These words were clarified through the decomposition of categories and subcategories reflected in the title of the study, to generate the answers to the research questions. The search strategies were meticulously adapted to the particularities of each database, using Boolean operators and temporal filters to circumscribe the results to publications from the last five years, thus guaranteeing the timeliness and relevance of the information analyzed.

In addition, rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria were implemented to optimize the processing of the information and to delimit the scope of the research, as shown in Table 2. These criteria are detailed in Table 2. After the meticulous selection of the studies, an exhaustive thematic coding was carried out,

identifying the main analytical categories related to intergenerational social mobility and the role of higher education. The data were subjected to an interpretative analysis using a comparative approach, highlighting convergences and divergences in countries in terms of the effects of university education on social mobility. Figure 1 shows the PRISMA flow diagram applied in the study.

Table 1. Database search engines

Database	Search equation
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(("social mobility" AND "university education") AND ("inequality" OR "economic outcomes"))
Web of Science	("higher education" AND "intergenerational mobility")
Eric	("social mobility" AND "university education") AND ("inequality")

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
- Articles published between 2014 and 2024.	- Non-peer-reviewed papers, such as technical reports, theses, or conference presentations.
- Articles in English.	- Studies that do not focus on university education or that analyze other educational levels without direct reference to social mobility.
- Studies published in peer-reviewed academic journals.	- Research conducted outside the Latin American context.
- Research that addresses the relationship between university education and intergenerational social mobility in the world.	- Articles published before 2014 or after 2024.
- Empirical, comparative studies or critical reviews that include data analysis on social mobility.	

Figure 1. Search flowchart, based on the PRISMA method [22]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

After conducting the systematic review, 1,404 articles related to the objectives of this research were identified. According to the PRISMA procedure, 28 of these articles were selected for analysis, given their relevance to university education, social mobility, the relationship between these two variables, and the global situation, as shown in Table 3. From the 28 articles selected, a growing trend in the publication of research related to university education and social mobility can be observed in recent years.

Even after establishing a period of 10 years for the document search, it was possible to obtain relevant information that met the selection criteria from the year 2019. In this first year, two articles were included for review; in 2020, this number increased to eight documents. Then, in 2021, four articles were registered, whereas in 2022 and 2023, five were tabulated, respectively. Finally, in 2024, the review concluded with four articles, as shown in Figure 2.

Table 3. PRISMA procedure

Stages of the PRISMA process	Number of items
Identification	1404
Eligibility	781
Screening	753
Included	28

Figure 2. Frequency of publication per year

Table 4 (see Appendix) [24]–[51] shows a summary of the findings obtained from the review of the 28 articles selected for the final analysis. The year of publication, author(s), objective, type of study, and the contribution generated are shown. This information represents how the possibility of bias can be elucidated when selecting the most relevant documents associated with the objective and main research question.

From the information obtained, it is possible to observe relevant characteristic aspects such as scientific production according to the journal and its corresponding quartile. In this sense, it was detected that 75.00 % (No.=21) corresponds to Q1 quartile indexed journals; 17.85 % (No.=5) corresponds to Q2 level journals; Q3 quartile is represented by 7.14 % (No.=2), and Q4 quartile, by 0 % (No.=0). Similarly, the journals with the highest participation were Social Science Research and Research in Social Stratification and Mobility, both located in the United States of America. This information is reflected in Table 5.

3.2. Discussion

3.2.1. Current role of higher education in intergenerational social mobility

Within a critical, reflective, and comparative framework, Zimmerman [27] highlights that estimates indicate students from private high schools following the same curriculum are 126% more likely to manage the same firms as their peers compared to non-peers. On the other hand, students who did not attend private institutions have a lower probability of managing firms with their peers rather than with non-peers. These findings do not align easily with explanations based on general or firm-specific human capital accumulation. Therefore, it is essential to emphasize that these effects result from higher success rates in business-oriented university careers. Lastly, variations in returns based on socio-economic status and gender cannot be readily linked to differences in academic performance or specific characteristics of the Chilean labor market.

University education stands as a fundamental pillar in the development of contemporary societies and encompasses the pedagogical and professional training processes developed within the higher education system. This training, provided in universities and specialized institutes, is structured at the undergraduate, master’s, and doctoral levels, to transmit theoretical knowledge, technical competencies, and advanced analytical skills within specific academic fields. In the context of 21st-century globalization, excellence-oriented university education has acquired unprecedented importance, even in critical and conflicting social, political and cultural environments [21]. University credentials have become a prerequisite for accessing quality employment, facilitating upward social mobility, and participating fully in decision-making spheres in most countries.

Table 5. Impact of the documents used in the study

Journal	Quartile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Journal of Economic Growth	Q1	1	4
Economic Systems	Q2	1	3.57
Structural Change and Economic Dynamics	Q1	1	3.57
American Economic Review	Q1	1	3.57
Labour Economics	Q1	1	3.57
Frontiers in Sociology	Q1	1	3.57
Asian Ethnicity	Q1	1	3.57
Contemporary Economic Policy	Q2	1	3.57
International Journal of Educational Development	Q1	1	3.57
American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics	Q1	1	3.57
European Sociological Review	Q1	1	3.57
Journal of South Asian Development	Q3	1	3.57
Journal of Asian and African Studies	Q2	1	3.57
Public Health	Q1	1	3.57
Social Forces	Q1	1	3.57
European Economic Review	Q1	1	3.57
Research in Social Stratification and Mobility	Q1	2	7.14
Campbell Systematic Reviews	Q1	1	3.57
Journal of Public Economics	Q1	1	3.57
Sociology Compass	Q1	1	3.57
Advances in Life Course Research	Q2	1	3.57
Social Science Research	Q1	1	3.57
Journal of Aging and Health	Q1	1	3.57
Econometría	Q1	1	3.57
European Sociological Review	Q1	1	3.57
Sociological Research Online	Q2	1	3.57
EconomiA	Q3	1	3.57
Total		28	100

Zheng and Graham [33], in terms of a calibrated structural model analysis, explain the importance of understanding the role of higher education in intergenerational mobility and the probability that a parent in the bottom income quintile will have a child in the bottom income quintile, which is essential for predicting and addressing economic inequality and providing broader access to opportunities for all citizens. Currently, no comprehensive research combines these areas to understand how interactions between students and institutions impact intergenerational mobility, leaving a significant gap for future studies. However, one of the most relevant findings is that, on average, both in economics and sociology, in terms of the impact of higher education on intergenerational mobility, the effect of parental status almost disappears for those who obtain a bachelor's degree. However, not all students who graduate from higher education obtain the same socioeconomic outcomes.

According to Kourtellos *et al.* [39], intergenerational mobility follows nonlinear patterns. Individuals with varying parental income levels experience different degrees of intergenerational mobility, and cognitive abilities contribute to explaining this phenomenon. From this standpoint, universities must gradually establish themselves as formal preparation centers where students and future professionals acquire the necessary skills to develop and sustain upward intergenerational trajectories, equipping them with effective tools as entrepreneurs.

Dräger [49] states that enrolling in a university program and earning a degree represents a significant challenge for individuals born and raised in low-income households. In this regard, his study's results suggest that parental wealth plays a crucial role in avoiding negative outcomes, such as leaving school without certification or failing to secure fully qualified vocational training. This is perceived as a characteristic of the higher education system which, in the absence of state intervention by promoting the creation of institutions sponsored by public investment, the scope of this level of training will be limited for the less favored classes. From the intergenerational aspect, it becomes a race with many obstacles, in which universities can be seen as elite and exclusive enclosures for the children or relatives of people of a significantly high socioeconomic level.

On the other hand, Sepúlveda and Lizama-Loyola [50] point out that many people face different barriers due to a lack of socioeconomic resources, previous educational disadvantages, class/ethnic discrimination, and family cultural background, while those of middle and upper class have to face different problems related to their families' expectations to maintain their social status. In contrast, research by Garcias and Kassouf [51] argue that, according to the documentary exploration carried out, the class origin of the parents represents a significant influence on the probability of accessing higher education in countries such as Brazil; when applying studies involving the use of conditional mathematical models, the democratization of access to universities does not show a sustained or deep trend.

3.2.2. Recent intergenerational social mobility patterns

Social mobility is a multifaceted phenomenon that has captured the attention of several scholars. It has been the focus of special policies in recent decades due to its profound impact on various aspects of modern societies. Consequently, it encompasses the dynamic changes in the socioeconomic positions of individuals, families, and groups over time, making it a crucial area of study for understanding social stratification and equality of opportunity. Doruk [26] findings indicate that intergenerational occupational mobility in Latin America remains largely associated with low-skilled jobs. This study confirms the region's historically low levels of social mobility, which, in turn, help explain its slow economic growth.

On the other hand, Duruk [26] argues that in Brazil, both married and single women have the highest intergenerational income transfer elasticity, while in Panama single men have a higher intergenerational income transfer elasticity. From the perspective of several researchers [24], [40], intergenerational social mobility is positively associated with a nation's economic growth and development. In essence, it refers to trends in social shifts of individuals or groups between different strata within a collectivity.

This movement can be upward or downward, depending on whether an individual's socioeconomic status improves or worsens relative to his or her starting point. The indicators used to measure this mobility usually include occupation, educational level, income level, and accumulated wealth. Therefore, when this change is seen between people of different generations, it is known as intergenerational mobility, in which an individual's socioeconomic position is compared with that of his or her family of origin.

Concerning upward intergenerational social mobility, Alesina *et al.* [48] points out that opportunities vary substantially between different areas, continents, and regions of the same country. This is greater in regions that showed a higher level of development at the historical moment of independence, with greater urbanization and employment in the service-manufacturing sector. In Africa, the conditions of the regions are crucial for having an acceptable quality education and have a positive impact on intergenerational mobility.

However, Surmeier *et al.* [47] notes that in the United States, older Americans, Hispanics, and Afro-Americans have shown greater educational gains relative to their parents compared to whites. This allows inferring that there is a propensity for intergenerational mobility advancement, depending on the ethnicity or race of the individual. However, as Hispanic individuals continue to attain higher levels of education, it is unclear whether upward mobility will translate into positive or negative assimilation consequences. In this approach, when children attain higher socioeconomic status than their parents, it is often considered a positive indicator of social progress and opportunity.

As for downward mobility, Alesina *et al.* [48] argues that it represents a decline in status between generations and may indicate difficulties in maintaining socioeconomic positions. Horizontal mobility occurs when individuals maintain a status like that of their parents, whereas immobility represents a direct inheritance of socioeconomic status across generations. The prevalence of these different types of mobility within a society can provide information about its overall social structure and the degree of opportunities it offers to its citizens.

According to Mare and Song [42], intergenerational mobility takes multiple forms and produces various effects. It can function through the process of mobility and position attainment itself or through demographic factors—such as marriage, fertility, and mortality—that influence intergenerational socioeconomic reproduction. Likewise, they add the inequality of opportunities between men and women to this context, emphasizing that socially men manage to achieve a higher socioeconomic status and that, in addition, men of generations before the one observed conceived more children who were able to overcome barriers to reach a productive age.

Consistent with the findings of Heckman and Landersø [28], it is predominantly children from well-educated families who drive university expansion. For children of parents with university degrees, completion rates have been found to be between 30% and 60%, demonstrating the Matthew effect (people with resources accumulate more resources). On the other hand, the main factor affecting intergenerational social mobility is education, which acts as an important determinant due to its crucial role in the conception of equal opportunities and the promotion of human capital formation [30]–[32]. However, the lack of education represents a vehicle that drives inequalities. Access to high-quality education for the entire population is fundamental to creating upward mobility pathways and breaking the cycle of intergenerational poverty. In that sense, public policies and social spending in areas such as health, housing, and social protection also play a vital role in mitigating the effects of socioeconomic background on an individual's life chances. In addition, factors such as discrimination, income distribution, and geographic location can significantly affect mobility patterns within a society.

One somewhat uncommon pattern observed in intergenerational social mobility involves smoking. Gugushvili *et al.* [37] analyzed the relationship between intergenerational educational mobility and tobacco consumption. Based on nationally representative samples from 20 European countries, the study found that both parental and individual education significantly influenced smoking habits among women, while among men, only individual education played a significant role.

Specifically, women who achieved higher education levels than their parents had a lower likelihood of becoming regular smokers compared to those who remained at the same educational level. This outcome resulted from the combined benefits of higher education and the additional advantage of upward mobility. Conversely, individuals who attained lower education levels than their parents exhibited a higher probability of smoking, a trend linked to both lower education and the effects of downward mobility. Furthermore, the impact of downward mobility generally exceeded that of upward mobility. These findings remained consistent regardless of the model specifications applied in the analysis.

It is important to highlight the contributions of intergenerational practices to social mobility. It is in this construct that Campbell *et al.* [41] highlight the fact that the dynamic and programmed interaction between members of different non-family generations in the educational and work environment promotes the attitude of the new generations to push themselves toward promotion to other academic levels. In the same way, it is inclined to improve socioeconomic status, in which understanding and respect, regardless of the current position, allows pointing out a positive relational behavioral pattern of ascending character.

Social mobility remains a fundamental aspect of social development and individual well-being. Its study and promotion are essential for creating more equitable, efficient, and cohesive societies. As research in this field continues to evolve, it will be crucial that policymakers, educators, and community leaders work together to implement evidence-based strategies that enhance social mobility and create genuine opportunities for all members of society to reach their full potential.

Finally, when reviewing first- and second-generation behavior, African Americans and Hispanics had more difficulty accessing higher education, suggesting that racial differences and migration background may interfere with social mobility [44]–[46]. In this way, physical characteristics imply a factor that may impair the transgenerational social mobility of some people. Accordingly, Afro-Hispanics and Hispanics had more difficulties in accessing higher education and faced social barriers.

3.2.3. Perspectives on intergenerational social mobility

The appreciation of aspects of intergenerational social mobility over time has generated the need to explore the extent and depth of intergenerational social mobility in family growth and development. Neumeyer and Pietrzyk [29] show that, in higher education in Germany, some groups of immigrant graduates make a stronger effort to continue their university studies than native graduates. These groups are found to be of the same social background and similar level of achievement. This is striking because it has been shown - in Germany-that the educational level of parents strongly influences the educational trajectories of their children. However, natives make more ambitious choices than immigrants.

In Latin America, Neidhöfer *et al.* [24] determined that intergenerational mobility has shown an overall increase. This trend appears to stem from the high upward mobility of individuals from families with low educational backgrounds, while significant immobility persists among those at the upper end of the socioeconomic spectrum. This evidence highlights the connection between educational attainment and economic well-being in the region. To illustrate this, average income levels are presented for six broad educational categories, along with education-related income disparities. The analysis compares income differences between highly educated and less educated individuals across younger and older cohorts in each Latin American Country. Although substantial variations exist between countries, higher education levels consistently correlate with higher income levels.

In comparison with behavior in Asia, Murshed and Uddin [35] mention that in Bangladesh it is possible to observe that children are less likely to progress beyond their parents' levels of education. Similarly, certain divergences in intergenerational educational mobility were corroborated for daughters compared to sons, and for children of more educated parents compared to children of less educated parents. The quality of education plays an important role here. Nguyen and Nguyen [36] point out that in Vietnam, sectors representing the minority receive reduced and waived tuition fees. However, in tuition, fees represent a relatively small proportion of total education spending. Thus, to boost intergenerational social mobility, the state can provide subsidies and preferential loans to lower-income students.

In the spatial case of the European continent, there are powerful forces that create inequalities in educational attainment and, in turn, mobility opportunities, which are largely beyond political reach [38], [43], [50]. In this, family groups with better socio-cultural and educational positions are favored to participate without much effort in the so-called "concerted cultivation" of children, which refers to a full and possible expression of their academic and human potential at its maximum expression. Finally, these families are geographically and culturally related to the group of Western Nordic Countries, comprising France, Germany, Ireland, and the United Kingdom; it is these nations that are closest to the upper limit of trans-generational social mobility growth.

4. CONCLUSION

The literature reviewed shows a significant relationship between intergenerational social mobility and university education, where the socioeconomic factor plays a determining role in access and academic results. Students from privileged backgrounds have advantages in performance, graduation rates and employment opportunities, reinforcing pre-existing inequalities. Although the expansion of higher education has improved its coverage, it has not been sufficient to correct these disparities. The segmentation of the university system can perpetuate or, in some cases, mitigate initial differences, calling into question the idea of education as an effective social equalizer.

While university graduates tend to experience upward mobility, its magnitude varies by social background, with those from professional or academic families better able to capitalize on their credentials. Factors such as the unequal distribution of capital, socio-cultural differences and access to influential networks limit the ability of education to reduce social gaps. This challenges the simplistic view of education as a driver of equality and highlights the need for more targeted policies that not only expand access to college, but also remove barriers along the entire educational trajectory. Thus, longitudinal studies and labor integration programs could provide valuable evidence on the evolution of social mobility in different contexts.

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : **O**riting - **O**riginal Draft

E : **E**riting - **R**eview & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data availability is not applicable to this paper as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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APPENDIX

Table 4. Details of the articles selected for analysis

Ref.	Objective of study	Type of study	Contributions
[24]	To explore the relationship between social mobility and economic development in Latin America	Longitudinal, mixed, analytical, and correlational study.	Findings show that rising social mobility is linked to economic growth in Latin America.
[25]	To examine intergenerational transmission in six underserved Latin American economies.	Mixed empirical approach study, using the multinomial logit model (MNL model).	Parent-to-child occupational transmission was higher in Panama (administrative) and Costa Rica (agricultural), but lower in Brazil.
[26]	To model intergenerational income linkages in rural and urban areas.	Empirical study with a mixed approach.	Results across models suggest prior studies greatly overestimated intergenerational mobility in Panama and Brazil.
[27]	Check whether elite universities help students who do not belong to historically advantaged groups to reach the top positions in the economy.	Quantitative, empirical study.	Leadership gaps among peers from similar backgrounds suggest that peer ties may play a key role.
[28]	Analyze the lessons for Americans from Denmark on inequality and social mobility.	Retrospective-comparative study on the intergenerational transmission of welfare	Family influence on children's development in Denmark resembles that in the U.S., with shared factors hard to offset—even with Denmark's generous welfare.
[29]	To compare the level of decision-making between immigrants and natives after completing their postgraduate studies in Germany.	Quantitative approach, of an applied type using the survey technique.	Lacking parental wealth, some immigrant graduates strive harder to continue studying than native-born peers with similar backgrounds and achievement levels.
[30]	To examine the effect of academic qualifications and network linkages on the evolution of Indian micro, small, medium and large ethnic firms in Malaysia.	Retrospective study collecting and analyzing literature and past evidence on Indian ethnic entrepreneurship in Malaysia.	Findings show that academic qualifications passed through generations influence how entrepreneurs connect with family.
[31]	To analyze the intergenerational transmission of education in nine sub-Saharan African countries.	A mixed, empirical and evaluative approach	Parental education strongly influences children's outcomes, with daughters in sub-Saharan Africa more closely tied to parents' education than sons.
[32]	A literature review of empirical studies conducted in China	A review of higher education expansion and graduate employment in China.	In the expansion of higher education, promoting social mobility has never been a role that higher education expansion was obliged to play from the outset. Micro-level measures could hardly alter the macro-level direction.

Table 4. Details of the articles selected for analysis (*continued*)

Ref.	Objective of study	Type of study	Contributions
[33]	Explain the factors associated with inequality in public education and intergenerational mobility.	Applied type study, through an analysis of a structural model calibrated using as variables social mobility.	Children in poor areas with lower-quality schools face reduced mobility, while better-funded schools offer stronger education and lead to higher adult incomes.
[34]	How lifelong learning offers second chances to staff from disadvantaged social backgrounds, with an alternative route to high qualifications.	Retrospective study based on the qualifications of individuals included in British births in 1970.	Men and women from disadvantaged backgrounds, especially if they have high skills, are indeed competent to raise their qualification levels. However, they do so through the attainment of more demonstrated qualities at the vocational level, rather than through academic records.
[35]	Understanding the trend in intergenerational educational mobility in the context of Bangladesh.	An empirical study with a two-stage stratified cluster sampling design with regression estimates.	Educational mobility differs by gender and by parents' educational level, with gaps between sons, daughters, and children from varying family backgrounds.
[36]	To examine intragenerational and intergenerational mobility of employment and earnings in Vietnam over the period 2004-2014.	Quantitative empirical study using mathematical modeling and OLS regression.	The results of this study suggest that the government should prioritize access to higher education and vocational training, especially for the most vulnerable sectors, such as the poor and ethnic minorities.
[37]	To examine the association of intergenerational educational mobility and smoking.	Quantitative empirical study through the application of diagonal reference models.	Gender gaps in how parental education and mobility affect smoking relate to differing educational levels and their links to health behaviors.
[38]	To broaden the perspective and provide an updated description of intergenerational class mobility rates in thirty European countries.	Quantitative study of comparative scope based on the European Social Survey.	Absolute mobility rates vary considerably according to national differences in the extent and pattern of structural class change. Countries are grouped into categories of relatively high or low fluidity, within which there is remarkable cross-national similarity.
[39]	Analysis of economic mobility patterns and their level of heterogeneity among socioeconomic groups.	Standard empirical study, with the linear GSE model, with linear regression.	Intergenerational mobility presents non-linear patterns. Individuals with different levels of parental income experience varying degrees of intergenerational mobility.
[40]	To analyze four different approaches to the study of how individuals' income and education during adulthood are related to their family background.	An empirical qualitative approach with analytical and comparative scope.	Comparing approaches offers a clearer view of family background's role; scholars in each subfield should consider research from the others.
[41]	Evaluate evidence on the use of intergenerational practice.	In-depth literature review between July 22 and July 30, 2021.	Evidence suggests that intergenerational activity can have a positive impact on participants, reducing loneliness and exclusion among both older people and children and young people.
[42]	Analyze the variety of intergenerational effects considering four generational changes.	Empirical, illustrative, and exploratory study of novel historical data.	Marriage and fertility gaps suggest inequality persists, as men from advantaged families more easily attain high social status.
[43]	Characterizing intergenerational mobility in Germany using census data on educational level and parental income.	Empirical study with a quantitative, comparative and longitudinal approach.	At the regional level, there is substantial variation in mobility estimates. Local characteristics, rather than classification patterns, explain most of these differences.
[44]	Emphasize the need to take into account a more holistic measure of the socioeconomic context in intergenerational mobility research.	Review of the literature on intergenerational mobility.	When observing the behavior of the first and second generations, both African and Hispanic people faced greater difficulties in accessing higher education, with fewer opportunities compared to other groups.
[45]	To examine the association of social mobility and health in a unique sample of the Russian population after the transition to a market society.	Qualitative approach through a retrospective cross-sectional study.	The objective characteristics of individuals only partially explain the variation in their subjective perceptions of social mobility, which is closely related to health outcomes.
[46]	To examine the association between parental education and children's entry into school, based on the 2010, 2013, 2015, and 2017 National Survey of College Graduates.	Qualitative approach through a retrospective cross-sectional study.	Those from high socioeconomic backgrounds are more likely to earn college degrees, attend selective institutions, major in lucrative fields, and complete their education at a younger age.
[47]	To analyze the impact of intergenerational on the overall life satisfaction of older Hispanic, White, and African Americans.	Retrospective qualitative approach study.	Hispanics report the highest life satisfaction, but intergenerational mobility loses significance when education and other factors are considered.

Table 4. Details of the articles selected for analysis (*continued*)

Ref.	Objective of study	Type of study	Contributions
[48]	To analyze intergenerational mobility (IM) in educational attainment in Africa since independence, using census data.	Mixed approach with applied research and the analytical-predictive method.	Mobility is highest in the most developed regions at the time of independence, with higher levels of urbanization and employment in the service and manufacturing sectors.
[49]	To assess whether educational attainment in Germany is stratified by parental wealth and at which transition stratification emerges.	Mixed-approach, applied, cross-sectional, evaluative-comparative study.	Students from wealthy households are 20% more likely to attend high-performing schools and obtain more advanced school certifications, as well as 40% more likely to enroll in higher education.
[50]	To explore the relationship between people's trajectories and their college experiences.	Qualitative approach study with a retrospective scope.	Working-class respondents face barriers such as a lack of socioeconomic resources, prior educational disadvantages, and class or ethnic discrimination.
[51]	To analyze intergenerational mobility in education and occupation and the effect of schooling on young people's earnings in Brazil	This is a quantitative, applied and comparative study, with a logarithmic model.	Around 57% of the youth in our sample whose parents had at most primary education had secondary education, and 5% had university or postgraduate degrees.

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